

Machine Learning Models for Predicting Electricity Demand in Spain.

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Abstract— This study presents the process of modeling and evaluating various machine learning algorithms for predicting electricity demand in Spain, using integrated information from three independent data sources. The main objective was to determine whether predictive performance improved by incorporating climate variables, energy source characteristics, and electricity market prices into the modeling process. To this end, four supervised models were implemented and compared: linear regression, support vector machine (SVM), random forest, and XGBoost. Prior to training the models, an exploratory data analysis was performed to identify a small number of missing values, which were corrected by interpolation in order to preserve the consistency and quality of the database. The results obtained allow for an analysis of the contribution of each set of variables and highlight the advantages and limitations of each modeling approach for energy demand forecasting.

Index of Terms—Machine learning, linear regression, support vector, random forest, XGBoost, electricity demand, energy, climate variables, market prices, predictive modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustained growth in energy demand and the increasing integration of renewable sources into electrical systems have created new challenges for energy system planning and operation. In this context, accurate electricity demand forecasting has become key to ensuring system stability, optimizing generation resources, and improving grid operational efficiency.

Traditionally, demand forecasts have been based on linear statistical models or time series techniques. However, these approaches have limitations in capturing the complexity and nonlinear nature of electricity consumption patterns, which are influenced by multiple factors such as weather conditions, day

of the week, season of the year, and socioeconomic variations.

In recent years, advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning have enabled the development of more robust and adaptive models capable of identifying nonlinear relationships and hidden patterns in large volumes of data. These techniques offer a significant improvement in predictive capabilities compared to conventional methods, contributing to more efficient and sustainable energy management.

The objective of this study is to predict electricity demand in Spain based on historical data on consumption, prices, electricity generation, and meteorological variables, using artificial intelligence models. To this end, four supervised learning algorithms were implemented: linear regression, support vector machine (SVM), random forest, and XGBoost, whose respective performance metrics and accuracy in estimating future demand were analyzed in detail. The comparative evaluation of these models made it possible to identify the influence of climatic variables and their relationship with electricity consumption behavior, providing valuable information for decision-making and planning in the energy sector.

II. BACKGROUND

a. Machine Learning-Based Energy Demand Prediction [1].

This study analyzed the prediction of daily energy demand by applying multiple regression models, artificial neural networks, and hybrid machine learning approaches that incorporated climate variables. The study developed a hybrid model that integrated historical consumption and weather data with the aim of improving the accuracy of demand estimates. The results showed that the model achieved a mean square error of less than 3%, outperforming traditional statistical methods. In conclusion, the integration of meteorological information with machine learning techniques significantly improved the predictive capacity of models in the field of electricity demand.

b. Evaluation of Electrical Load Demand Forecasting Using Various ML Algorithms [2]

It evaluated the performance of different machine learning algorithms applied to electricity demand forecasting, including support vector machines, random forests, extreme gradient boosting, and long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks. The study compared the results obtained by each model, showing that the LSTM and extreme gradient boosting methods achieved the lowest average error, close to 2%. The authors concluded that deep learning models showed a greater ability to capture nonlinear and temporal patterns in the data, significantly outperforming classical prediction approaches.

c. Systematic Review of Deep Learning and Machine Learning Techniques for Energy Load Prediction [3]

They conducted a systematic review of more than 80 studies in which machine learning and deep learning techniques were applied to forecast energy demand, both in the short and long term. This research analyzed various models, including neural networks, long short-term memory (LSTM), random forest, support vector regression, and gated recurrent unit (GRU). The results showed that LSTM and GRU architectures performed better in short-term predictions. It was also concluded that deep learning-based models achieved greater accuracy than traditional methods, although they required greater computational capacity and more rigorous parameter adjustment.

The review shows that, although traditional approaches such as linear regression and support vector machines (SVM) persist, models based on decision trees, boosting, and recurrent neural networks have become more relevant in recent years. These methods stand out for their ability to model nonlinear relationships and capture complex temporal patterns in time series, outperforming traditional techniques in short-term electricity demand forecasting.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Currently, transmission system operators (TSOs) make daily forecasts of electricity demand using mainly traditional statistical models, such as linear regression or time series methods. However, the growing development of renewable energy sources characterized by high variability and dependence on weather conditions has increased the complexity of the system and, consequently, the uncertainty in demand estimates. In addition, factors such as climate change, diversification of energy consumption, and the integration of new distributed resources have generated less predictable behavior patterns, driving the need to implement more robust and adaptive approaches to improve the accuracy of electricity projections.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTION

¿ Is it possible to forecast electricity demand 24 hours in advance with greater accuracy than the transmission system operator (TSO)?

V. OBJETIVE

The objective of this project is to evaluate the ability of machine learning models to predict electricity demand in Spain 24 hours in advance and determine whether these models can exceed the accuracy of the official forecast issued by the system operator (TSO – Red Eléctrica de España). To do this, a machine learning-based approach is used to analyze the relationship between consumption variables, electricity

generation, and weather conditions. The performance of the models will be compared with the TSO forecast.

VI. EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS

The Hourly Energy Consumption, Generation, Prices, and Weather dataset collects hourly information on Spain's electricity system over a four-year period. For its development, it considered three main sources:

- ENTSO-E, it has information on electricity consumption and generation records (actual and forecasted).
- Red Eléctrica de España (REE) contains the hourly electricity prices.
- OpenWeather API provides weather variables (temperature, humidity, wind, etc.) for the main cities in the country.

This dataset allows for analyzing the relationship between weather conditions, energy consumption, electricity generation, and prices. It also provides the possibility of comparing the official forecasts of the system operator (TSO) with the actual recorded values.

Analyzing data on consumption, electricity generation, prices, and climatic variables is essential to understand the functioning of the energy system and move towards more efficient management, as well as to identify patterns of demand and production. Moreover, it helps optimize supply planning and facilitate the integration of renewable sources, whose generation depends on weather conditions. It also contributes to improving the stability of the electrical system, anticipating fluctuations in energy prices, and supporting informed decision-making both at the operational and energy policy levels. Additionally, applying artificial intelligence models in this field is a key tool to drive the transition towards a smarter, more economical, and environmentally friendly energy model.

The dataset has 29 columns and 35,064 records with hourly information related to various aspects of the Spanish electrical system. The included variables are related to:

- The weather
- Electricity generation (renewable and non-renewable)
- Hydroelectric
- Weather forecasts
- Demand (usage)
- Prices

In the dataset, eight variables were identified that do not provide relevant information for the study, so they were excluded from the analysis. Similarly, some variables with a percentage of missing values below 1% were detected, which were also removed in order to ensure the quality and consistency of the information used. Finally, the dataset consisted of 35,018 records and 21 columns.

On the other hand, a database related to meteorological variables was incorporated, considering that these factors historically influence electricity generation levels depending on the type of energy source used. The database has 178,396 records. Variables associated with codes or those whose meaning was already detailed in other variables were excluded, thus avoiding redundancy in the information. In particular, the database includes information related to:

- Date and time
- Geographic location
- Temperature: current, minimum, and maximum
- Atmospheric pressure
- Relative humidity
- Wind speed and direction
- Precipitation: rainfall in 1 hour and 3 hours
- Snowfall in 3 hours
- Cloud cover

The descriptive analysis of meteorological variables shows that the average temperature is 289.6 Kelvin, with minimum values of 262.2 K and maximum values of 315.6 K, while the minimum and maximum temperatures have averages of 288.3 K and 291.1 K, respectively, with similar ranges. Atmospheric pressure averages 1,069.3 hPa and shows high variability, reflected in an atypical maximum value of 100,831 hPa. Relative humidity has an average value of 68.4% and wind speed averages 2.5 m/s, with directions centered at 166.6°. In terms of precipitation and cloud cover, the average accumulated rainfall in 1 hour is very low (0.1 mm), snowfall in 3 hours is also minimal (0.2 mm), and cloud cover averages 25.1%, ranging from 0 to 100%.

Descriptives	temp	temp_min	temp_max	pressure	humidity	wind_speed	wind_deg	rain_1h	rain_3h	snow_3h	clouds_all
count	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0	178.396,0
mean	289,6	288,3	291,1	1.069,3	68,4	2,5	166,6	0,1	-	-	25,1
std	8,0	8,0	8,6	5.969,6	21,9	2,1	116,6	0,4	0,0	0,2	30,8
min	262,2	262,2	262,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25%	283,7	282,5	284,7	1.013,0	53,0	1,0	55,0	-	-	-	-
50%	289,2	288,2	290,2	1.018,0	72,0	2,0	177,0	-	-	-	20,0
75%	295,2	293,7	297,2	1.022,0	87,0	4,0	270,0	-	-	-	40,0
max	315,6	315,2	321,2	1.008.371,0	100,0	133,0	360,0	12,0	2,3	21,5	100,0

Figure 1. Study of meteorological database variables

On the other hand, outliers were identified in the wind pressure and speed variables, for which the interquartile range method was applied for their removal. In addition, data type transformations were carried out: the date variables were converted to the corresponding date format, and those that were in text but represented numbers were transformed into numeric values. In this regard, duplicate records were removed, and a new database was obtained in which the average of each variable per hour was calculated, resulting in a total of 35,064 records.

Figure 2. Distribution of electricity demand

Figure 2 shows the distribution of electricity demand in Spain, with two main peaks in consumption levels, indicating the existence of time periods with higher electrical activity. In this regard, on average, demand is around 28,696.9 MWh. The distribution does not have heavy tails, indicating that extreme values, both very high and very low, are infrequent within the dataset.

Figure 3. Average demand by day of the week

The behavior of electricity demand varies throughout the week, showing a decrease during weekends. On these days, energy production and consumption are lower compared to weekdays, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Average hourly demand

By analyzing the hourly electricity demand throughout the day in Figure 4, two main peaks are identified: the first around 10:00 a.m. and the second near 7:00 p.m., times when the highest electricity production and consumption are recorded. Conversely, during the early morning, especially between 2:00 and 3:00 a.m., the lowest generation level is observed. From 4:00 a.m. onwards, demand begins to gradually increase until reaching the first morning peak, then remaining within a stable range between 30,000 and 32,000 MWh until reaching the second peak in the evening hours.

Figure 5. Average monthly demand

Figure 5 shows the monthly behavior of electricity demand. It is observed that the maximum consumption occurs in the months of January, which corresponds to winter, when low temperatures increase the use of heating, while July falls in summer, a period in which consumption rises due to the intensive use of cooling systems. On the other hand, the months with the lowest demand occur in the spring (April and May) and autumn (October) seasons. These periods are characterized by more moderate temperatures, which reduce the need for heating or cooling and, consequently, decrease electricity consumption.

Taking into account the breakdown of electricity demand, Figure 6 presents a heat map in which red tones indicate periods

of highest electricity demand, while blue tones reflect times of lowest consumption. In this regard, and in line with what is observed in Figures 2 and 3, peaks in demand are identified around 10:00 a.m. and 7:00 p.m., corresponding to the hours of highest daily activity.

Figure 6. Weekday electrical demand vs. Hour

Figure 6 allows us to visualize the behavior of demand according to the time of day and the day of the week, showing that during lunch and dinner hours the population tends to consume more energy than usual. This pattern also continues on weekends, although with a significantly lower level of consumption. Finally, it is observed that Sunday is the day with the lowest electricity demand, while Wednesday records the highest consumption levels..

Figure 7. Distribution of electricity demand on working days and non-working days

Figure 7 shows the distribution of electricity demand, differentiating between weekdays and weekends. It can be seen that demand is significantly higher on weekdays, mainly concentrated between 27,000 and 32,000 MWh, while on weekends consumption levels decrease, with values more frequently between 23,000 and 28,000 MWh. In addition, the distribution for weekdays shows two main peaks, reflecting the existence of hours of high demand associated with periods of greater daily activity, such as the morning and afternoon hours. Overall, the figure shows that economic and work activity directly influences electricity consumption behavior, which decreases considerably on weekends.

Figure 8. Electricity demand distribution by season

Figure 8 shows the distribution of electricity demand by season. It can be seen that demand is highest during the winter, reaching its most frequent values between 28,000 and 33,000 MWh, reflecting the increase in energy consumption associated with the use of heating systems. In contrast, during spring and fall, demand shows more moderate levels and a more uniform distribution, indicating more stable consumption. On the other hand, in summer, demand remains relatively high, although slightly lower than in winter, mainly influenced by the use of cooling equipment. In general, the figure shows the seasonal influence of the climate on electricity consumption behavior, with winter being the season of highest demand and the intermediate seasons (spring and fall) those of relatively lower consumption.

Figure 9. Demand and price relationship

Figure 9 shows the relationship between electricity demand and electricity prices in Spain. A positive relationship between the two variables is observed, indicating that as electricity demand increases, the price also tends to rise. This behavior is consistent with the dynamics of the electricity market, where higher demand usually puts upward pressure on energy prices.

Figure 10. Evolution of electricity demand

When analyzing the total energy demand and electricity generation together in Figure 10, it is apparent that both series follow a similar pattern over time. However, some outliers are identified in the generation data that fall below their usual pattern. It is also observed that generation consistently adjusts to demand levels, indicating a balanced relationship between the two variables and suggesting that there is no significant energy waste. Although demand always appears above generation in the data, this does not imply an energy deficit; rather, it reflects that there are additional sources and mechanisms in the electrical system that complement the recorded generation.

Figure 11. Correlation Matrix

Figure 11 shows the correlation between the variables, finding that: the relationship with electricity demand and generation reveals a moderate positive correlation with the current electricity price and with non-renewable generation, with coefficients of 0.44 and 0.54, respectively. This indicates that as demand increases, both the price and non-renewable generation tend to rise. On the other hand, renewable generation shows a moderate positive correlation of 0.42 with total demand, although with a smaller effect than non-renewable generation. Additionally, the relationship between price and renewable generation is weakly negative at -0.11, suggesting that renewable generation has little significant impact on the price.

Finally, a moderate negative correlation of -0.42 is observed between renewable and non-renewable generation, showing a substitution effect between the two sources of generation.

VII. MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

To address the research problem, various machine learning models were employed in order to identify which one provides the best fit for the electricity demand data in Spain. For each model developed, the dataset was split into training and test sets, allowing for a consistent evaluation of performance. In this context, four main models were used:

A. Linear Regression

A linear regression model was fitted to model the relationship between electricity demand and several independent variables. This type of model allows representing this relationship with a straight line, facilitating both the prediction of electricity demand in Spain and the analysis of how climatic variables and electricity generation sources interact and affect such demand. The approach to developing the model was based on applying a time lag to the data series so that the model could learn to use the information available at the current hour (t) to predict the electricity demand corresponding to the same hour of the following day ($t+24$). In this case, the target column was shifted 24 rows upward, so that each record in the dataset is associated with the demand value that will occur 24 hours later. The following variables were considered for the prediction: renewables, no renewables, price actual, hour, month, weekday_idx, temp, humidity, wind_speed.

The metrics obtained indicate that the model has limited performance in predicting electricity demand, as the MAE yielded a value of 2,699.6 and the RMSE of 3,477, which shows considerable errors, especially at peak demand, where the model tends to fail more pronouncedly. Likewise, the R^2 value shows that the model only explains 43.3% of the data variability, reflecting moderate predictive capacity and the need to improve its fit by incorporating new variables, better hyperparameter optimization, or more robust models.

Figure 12. Linear regression prediction

Graph 12 shows that the model adequately captures periods when demand is low or varies moderately. However, when demand peaks occur, the model fails to adjust accurately and tends to underestimate actual values. Although a linear regression model is being used, there is some alignment with

the general trend of the data, which shows that demand behavior is not strictly linear. It is important to note that the blue line represents actual energy demand in Spain, while the orange line corresponds to the values estimated by the model.

B. Support Vector Machine

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) model was adjusted with the aim of predicting electricity demand in Spain, which captured complex relationships between the dependent variable (electricity demand) and independent variables, including climatic factors and sources of electricity generation. Unlike linear regression, SVMs can handle both linear and nonlinear relationships, making it easier to understand how the variables interact and how they influence electricity demand.

For the 24-hour electricity demand forecast, a Support Vector Regression (SVR) model was implemented. First, a series of lagged variables of electricity consumption were constructed over different time horizons (1, 2, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 72, 96, and 168 hours), along with moving windows of 24 and 168 hours, as well as the change in consumption compared to the value recorded 24 hours earlier. Additionally, cyclical time transformations (sine and cosine) were incorporated to capture daily and monthly seasonality, and variables related to renewable and non-renewable generation, day-of-the-week indicators, and weather conditions (temperature and humidity) were added. The target variable was defined as the energy demand shifted 24 hours ahead.

Due to the sensitivity of the SVR algorithm to the scale of the variables, both the input features and the target variable were standardized before training. Subsequently, an SVR model with an RBF kernel was implemented, which allows the data to be transformed into a higher-dimensional space, making it easier to capture patterns and nonlinear relationships present in the data. To improve predictive performance, tuned parameters $C = 5$, $\epsilon = 0.05$, and $\gamma = \text{scale}$ were used, which respectively control the error penalty, the tolerance margin, and the influence of each sample in the RBF kernel.

Finally, predictions were generated on the test set and rescaled to their original values to calculate the metrics. The model achieved an MAE of 1,605.6 MW, an RMSE of 2,359.9 MW, and an R^2 of 0.739, which indicates that the SVR was able to explain nearly 74% of the variability in demand and had a significantly lower error level compared to simpler models.

Figura 13. SMV Prediction

Graph 13 shows that the support vector machine model provides a fit that is significantly closer to the actual values, demonstrating superior predictive performance compared to

less complex models. In general terms, the SVR is capable of adequately capturing the behavior patterns of electricity demand; however, limitations are observed in estimating very high demand peaks, particularly when they occur abruptly after periods of low or stable consumption. In contrast, when the series exhibits regular alternations between high and low levels, the model shows a more robust adaptation capability, producing consistently more accurate predictions.

C. Random Forest

A Random Forest model was fitted based on a set of multiple decision trees, allowing it to capture nonlinear relationships and complex patterns between the dependent variable (electricity demand) and various independent variables. Thanks to its multiple-tree structure, the model improves predictive ability and robustness against overfitting, while also facilitating the identification of the relative importance of each variable in the prediction.

For the construction of electric demand prediction models, three sets of independent variables were defined. Model 1 included variables related to electricity generation (renewables, non_renewables), temporal and seasonal information (weekday_idx, sin_hour, cos_hour, sin_month, cos_month), demand lags (load_t_24, load_t_168), and the proportion of renewable generation (renewables_ratio). Model 2 expanded the previous set by incorporating relevant weather variables, specifically temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed. Finally, Model 3 considered a more comprehensive set of features, including total generation, multiple demand lags (load_t_1, load_t_2, load_t_3, load_t_6, load_t_12, load_t_24, load_t_48, load_t_72, load_t_96, load_t_168), moving averages of load (load_ma_24, load_ma_168), 24-hour changes in demand (load_change_24h), and calendar and seasonal variables (sin_hour, cos_hour, sin_month, cos_month, weekday_idx, is_weekend) y condiciones climáticas (temp, humidity).

The results obtained for the Random Forest models are presented in Table III, evaluating the accuracy in predicting electricity demand. Model 1 achieved a mean absolute error of 1,906.0 MW, a root mean square error (RMSE) of 2,588.9 MW, and an R^2 of 0.686, indicating a reasonable fit to the data. By incorporating additional weather variables in Model 2, a slight improvement in the MAE (1,848.9 MW) was observed, although the RMSE remained relatively similar (2,612.3 MW) and R^2 slightly decreased to 0.680, suggesting that the new variables contributed limited information to the model.

Finally, Model 3, which included a more comprehensive set of demand lags, moving averages, and temporal features, showed the best performance with an MAE of 1,626.6 MW, an RMSE of 2,298.7 MW, and an R^2 of 0.752, demonstrating that the incorporation of more detailed historical information and

calendar and weather variables significantly improves the model's ability to capture the variability of electricity demand.

D. XGBoost

This model uses an approach based on decision trees enhanced with gradient boosting techniques, which allows it to efficiently model nonlinear relationships, complex interactions between variables, and dynamic patterns present in time series.

As in the Random Forest model, the same data preparation procedure was applied for this model. The target variable of electric demand was shifted by 24 hours to define the prediction horizon, and temporal features were generated through lags of consumption over multiple intervals, along with moving averages and derived variables.

The same set of variables previously used in the Random Forest model was employed, with the aim of maintaining consistency in performance comparison. Variables related to electricity generation were included, distinguishing between renewable and non-renewable sources (renewables, no_renewables, generation_total), as well as demand lags up to 168 hours (load_t_1, load_t_2, load_t_3, load_t_6, load_t_12, load_t_24, load_t_48, load_t_72, load_t_96, load_t_168). Additionally, moving averages (load_ma_24, load_ma_168) and 24-hour load changes (load_change_24h) were incorporated. To capture temporal and seasonal patterns, calendar variables and cyclical components (weekday_idx, is_weekend, sin_hour, cos_hour, sin_month, cos_month) were added, along with relevant weather conditions such as temperature and humidity.

The metrics obtained to evaluate the performance of the XGBoost model show a mean absolute error of 1,507.7 MW and a root mean square error of 2,229.9 MW, indicating a reasonable fit to the magnitude of electricity demand. Additionally, the coefficient of determination was 0.767, showing that the model explains approximately 77% of the variability observed in the demand data. These results reflect that XGBoost achieves an appropriate balance between accuracy and generalization capability, being effective at capturing the trends and fluctuations of the electrical system.

Figure 13. Evolution of electricity demand

Figure 13 compares the actual electric demand with the prediction made by the XGBoost model. It can be seen that the prediction line closely follows the actual line, indicating that the model is able to capture the overall variability and fluctuations of the demand. Although it correctly shows the patterns of rises and falls, some very high and low peaks are not estimated with complete accuracy, suggesting that the model slightly smooths

the extremes but maintains the general behavior of the data. Additionally, it can be observed that it reproduces repetitive cyclic patterns, showing that it captures the daily and possibly weekly seasonality present in the demand. It also shows better tracking of complex curves, thanks to its ability to model nonlinear relationships and interactions between variables. On the other hand, the graph indicates that XGBoost provides robust and consistent predictions for electric demand, adequately fitting to the trends and variations of the system.

Table 1. Metrics of models used

Metrics	Regresión lineal	SVM	Random Forest1	Random Forest2	Random Forest3	XGBoost
MAE	2.699,6	1.606	1.906	1.849	1.627	1.508
RMSE	3,5	2.360	2.589	2.612	2.299	2.230
R ²	43,3%	73,9%	68,6%	68,0%	75,2%	76,7%

The results show that tree-based models, especially XGBoost, offer the best performance by achieving the lowest MAE and RMSE values and the highest R², indicating high predictive accuracy. The SVM model also demonstrates strong performance, clearly outperforming linear regression. In contrast, linear regression is the least effective model, with the highest errors and the lowest R², highlighting its inability to capture the complexity of the problem.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, various machine learning models were implemented and compared for predicting electricity demand in Spain. As a benchmark, traditional models were evaluated, including a linear regression model, which achieved an R² of 0.43, and a support vector machine (SVM) model, which reached an R² of 0.739, showing superior performance among linear methods. Subsequently, models based on decision trees were applied. In the case of Random Forest, three configurations were trained, achieving R² values of 0.686, 0.680, and 0.752, respectively, demonstrating a significant improvement over the linear models. Finally, the XGBoost model achieved the overall best performance with an R² of 0.767, showing a high capacity to capture non-linear relationships, seasonal variations, and demand peaks within the time series. Overall, these results confirm that nonlinear approaches vastly outperform traditional models in estimating electricity demand.

Among the various sets of variables evaluated, the inclusion of demand lags, moving averages, calendar variables, and weather conditions improved prediction accuracy, reflected in a lower MAE, a lower RMSE, and a higher coefficient of determination. In particular, XGBoost demonstrated a greater ability to model nonlinear relationships and capture peaks and troughs in demand, while Random Forest offered robustness and stability in prediction. These results show that ensemble methods represent a powerful alternative to traditional linear models, which, although interpretable, are often insufficient to capture the complexity and nonlinear nature of electricity demand.

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